

Carcinogenic Compounds : Synthesis of Polycyclic Carbazole Derivatives by Diels-Alder Reaction

S. P. HIREMATH*, S. S. KADDARGI and M. G. PUROHIT

Department of Chemistry, Karnatak University Post Graduate Centre, Gulbarga-585 105

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The 3-(β -nitrovinyl)benz(e)indole (1) has been reacted with various dienophiles, 1,4-benzoquinone, 1,4-naphthoquinone, N-phenylmaleimide, dimethyl acetylenedicarboxylate and tetracyanoethylene, under the conditions of Diels-Alder reaction to yield the polycyclic benzocarbazoles.

IN recent years the polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons have gained considerable interest owing to their carcinogenic properties. The carbazoles and benzocarbazoles, which have the structural similarity with polycyclic hydrocarbons, have also exhibited carcinogenic activity¹⁻⁵. A few methods are available in the literature for the synthesis of such compounds. Amongst them the synthesis using Diels-Alder reaction conditions between vinylindoles⁶ or nitrovinylindoles and dienophiles in polar solvents has been found to be most convenient. But the nitrovinylindoles are preferred to vinylindoles since the latter compounds are in most cases unstable and difficult to prepare. In our laboratory^{7,8} several such carbazole derivatives have been synthesised employing nitrovinylindoles as the dienes. In view of these facts and in continuation of our work on benzindoles⁹⁻¹¹, we report here the synthesis of benzocarbazole derivatives.

The 3-(β -nitrovinyl)benz(e)indole¹² (1) was prepared from benz(e)indole-3-carboxaldehyde by a base-catalysed condensation with nitromethane. The nitrovinylindole was reacted with various dienophiles such as 1,4-benzoquinone, 1,4-naphthoquinone, N-phenylmaleimide, dimethyl acetylenedicarboxylate and tetracyanoethylene in dioxan under refluxing conditions. The appearance of a brownish gas in the formation of 2, 3 and 4 immediately after the commencement of the reaction indicates that the condensation proceeded with the evolution of nitrous acid and its decomposed products. Simultaneously the aromatisation takes place—via a simple dehydrogenation to attain the ring stability. But in case of dimethyl acetylenedicarboxylate⁷ and tetracyanoethylene⁸ the Diels-Alder reaction took place without the evolution of brownish gas which indicates that in these cases the reaction proceeded with the retention of nitro group in the adduct.

The IR spectra of 2-4 exhibited bands at 3200 and around 1660 cm^{-1} due to NH and C=O fre-

quencies, respectively. The mass spectrum of com-

pound 3 exhibited the molecular ion peak at m/e 347 (m^+ , 100%), which confirms that aromatisation has taken place during the Diels-Alder reaction. Similar to the mass spectrum of benzoquinone, the peaks due to the favourable expulsion of CO from the molecular ion peak was observed at m/e 319 ($m^+ - \text{CO}$, 15.5%) and 291 ($m^+ - 2\text{CO}$, 18.2%). While studying the mass spectra of carbazoles, Riepe and

* To whom all the correspondence should be addressed.

Zander¹³ have reported the elimination of H₂CN molecule from the carbazole moiety. In this case also the peak at m/e 263 [(m⁺-2CO)-H₂CN, 6.7%] may be due to the favourable expulsion of H₂CN molecule from (m⁺-2CO) species. The peaks at m/e 348 (m⁺+1, 40%) and 349 (m⁺+2, 6.2%) may be due to the possible reduction of quinone to hydroquinone inside the heated inlet system of the spectrometer.

The ESR spectrum of the compound 2 has shown the expected 1:2:1 triplet. The free electrons from C=O of quinone have coupled with the adjacent proton of benzoquinone moiety to give rise to the above type of spectrum. This clearly indicates that the other part of the benzoquinone moiety has been fused with the diene (nitrovinyl system) to give 2. In the case of naphthoquinone adduct 3 the spectrum has shown a single peak, because the free electron of the anthraquinone system will have no scope for coupling with any protons as there are no protons in the ortho position. This confirms that in these cases the quinones have reacted with the diene in an usual Diels-Alder reaction fashion to give the expected adducts.

Experimental

The IR spectra were taken on a Perkin-Elmer Infracord and mass spectrum was recorded on AEI MS 902 spectrometer at 70 eV. The ESR spectra were taken by capillary method in THF.

13H-Dibenzo(a,i)carbazole-1,4-quinone (2)

The 3-(β-nitrovinyl)benz(e)indole (0.71 g, 0.003 mole) was dissolved in dry dioxan (25 ml). 1,4-Benzoquinone (0.64 g, 0.006 mole) was added to it and the mixture heated under reflux for 48 h. The solution was concentrated (10 ml) and the brown solid that separated was filtered and washed with boiling petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) to remove any unreacted benzoquinone present. The compound 2 crystallised from dioxan as reddish brown needles (0.65 g, 0.0021 mole, 72%), m.p. 236° (Found: C, 80.5; H, 3.4; N, 4.3 C₂₀H₁₁NO₂. Calc. C, 80.8; H, 3.7; N, 4.7%), νNH 3200w, νC=O 1650s, cm⁻¹ in nujol.

8,9-Benzonaphtho(2,3-i)carbazole(5,13)quinone (3)

This compound was prepared from 1 and 1,4-naphthoquinone (0.94 g, 0.006 mole) following the procedure described for 2. This crystallised from dioxan as pinkish shining needles (0.8 g, 0.0023 mole, 95%), m.p. 317° (Found: C, 82.5; H, 3.5; N, 4.4 C₂₄H₁₃NO₂. Calc. C, 82.9; H, 3.7; N, 4.4%), νNH 3200w, νC=O 1675s, cm⁻¹ in nujol; m/e 347 (m⁺, 100%), m/e 319 (m⁺-CO, 15.5%), m/e 291 (m⁺-2CO, 18.2%), m/e 263 [(m⁺-2CO)-H₂CN, 6.7%].

5,6-Benzocarbazole-1, 2-(N-phenyl)carboxamide (4)

This was prepared from 1 and N-phenylmaleimide (1 g, 0.006 mole) following the general procedure. The compound 4 crystallised from benzene as brown needles (0.6 g, 0.0026 mole, 89%), m.p. 145° (Found: C, 79.3; H, 3.4; N, 7.9 C₂₄H₁₄N₂O₂. Calc. C, 79.5; H, 3.8; N, 7.7%), νNH 3250w, νC=O 1720s, cm⁻¹ in nujol.

Dimethyl 6-nitro-3,4-benzo-7, 8-dicarboxylate (5)

This was obtained from 1 and dimethyl acetylene dicarboxylate (0.85 g, 0.006 mole) following the general procedure. 5 Crystallised from benzene as brown needles (0.6 g, 0.0015 mole, 58%), m.p. 184° (Found: C, 63.5; H, 3.8; N, 7.6 C₂₀H₁₄N₂O₆. Calc. C, 63.4; H, 3.7; N, 7.4%).

6-Nitro-8,9-dicyano-3,4-benzocarbazole (6)

A solution of 1 (0.71 g, 0.003 mole) and tetracyanoethylene (0.76 g, 0.006 mole) in dry benzene was kept at room temperature for 3 days. The solid that separated was filtered and washed with benzene. The compound 6 crystallised from dioxan as brown needles (0.65 g, 0.002 mole, 69%), m.p. 285° (Found: N, 17.5; C₁₈H₈N₄O₂. Calc. N, 17.3%).

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